

ASSESSMENT OF THE NUTRITIONAL COMPOSITION OF KETO-PANCAKE PRODUCED FROM AUBERGINE AND OAT FLOUR BLENDS

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ABSTRACT

This study was conducted to the nutritional composition of keto-pancake produced from aubergine and oat flour blends. Oat and aubergine were bought from Relief market. They were labeled as sample IMS, ISM, MIS and MSI respectively. IMS- Pancakes produced from 95% oat flour and 5% Aubergine flour, ISM- Pancakes produced from 90% oat flour and 10% Aubergine flour, MIS- Pancakes produced from 85% oat flour and 15% Aubergine flour, MSI- Pancakes produced from 80% oat flour and 20% Aubergine flour. The proximate composition, functional and sensory properties of the blends were determined using standard methods. The result of the proximate showed that moisture was highest in MSI (58.45%) and lowest in IMS (55.69%), Dry matter was highest in IMS (45.32%) and lowest in MSI (41.56%), ash content was highest in MIS (1.78%) and lowest in ISM(1.65%), protein was highest in MSI(5.30%) and lowest in ISM(4.34%), Fat have the highest in MSI (3.25%) and lowest IMS (1.84%), Fiber was highest in ISM(0.93%) and lowest in MIS(0.81%), carbohydrate was highest in highest in IMS(35.28%) and lowest in MSI (30.23%). The functional properties showed that bulk density, sample MIS has the lowest value of (0.539%) with sample IMS has the highest value of (0.604%), for true density, sample ISM has the lowest value of (0.295g/ml) while sample IMS has the highest value of (0.295g/ml), for emulsification capacity ranged 62.25% to 27.79% with sample MSI has the lowest value of (27.79%) while sample IMS has the highest value of (62.25%), for gelation capacity, sample MIS has the lowest value of (17.87%w/v) with sample MSI has the highest value of (18.78%w/v), for pH content, sample MSI having the lowest pH value of (5.00) while sample IMS having the highest value of (6.61),

water absorption, sample LSM has the lowest value of (10.38g/g) with sample MIS has the highest value of (11.97g/g), for oil absorption capacity, sample MSI has the lowest value of (9.36g/g) while sample LSM has the highest value of (9.67g/g), the sensory result ranged from 4.80 – 8.30 for color; 6.00 – 7.60, aroma 6.00 – 7.40 mouth feel and 5.10 – 7.20 general acceptability. The samples showed a significant difference $p < 0.05$ among themselves in terms of sensory properties. This study showed that production of keto-pancake from oat flour and aubergine flour can be produced but the inclusion of aubergine flour changes the colour of the keto-pancake but it can be edible but less in colour preferable.

Keywords- *Ketopancake, Aubergine, oat, Proximate, Functional, Sensory*

INTRODUCTION

Keto-Pancake is a flat, thin and round starch-based cake. It is prepared by pouring a fluid batter containing eggs, milk, baking powder, and other ingredients onto a hot surface and cooked until it bubbles and begin to puff, thereafter the other side is flipped and cooked until golden brown. (Hussein *et al.*, 2006). Keto-Pancakes are ready to eat convenient and inexpensive food product that is a widely consumed by all ages. They are high fat, adequate protein, low carbohydrate dietary therapy tin conventional medicine. Keto-Pancakes are starch-based products prepared by pouring batter onto a hot solid surface and cooking until solid. Pancakes, quick and flat snacks, are typically crafted from wheat flour. High-quality pancakes exhibit optimal swelling power, necessitating the use of fresh dough to meet quality standards. Eggplant (*Solanum melongena L.*) is an important solanaceous crop of sub tropics and tropics. The name brinjal is popular in Indian subcontinents and is derived from Arabic and Sanskrit whereas the name eggplant has been derived from the shape of the fruit of some varieties. Aubergine is a very noble source of vitamins B₁, B₆, A, C, K, niacin and folate. The occurrence of these vitamins in major quantities clarifies the importance of vitamin quantified in this vegetable.

Their beneficial effects include provision of normal visualization, cell growth and development gene expression, development of immunity role of body and maintenance of functions of epithelial cells. Numerous studies have exposed the vitamin C acts as antioxidant, which prevents cells from oxidative damage by reactive oxygen species. It is also significant for appropriate lung function and immunity (Okmen, *et al.*, 2009). Oats (*Avena sativa L*) are grown for use as grain as well as forage and fodder, straw for bedding, haylage, silage and chaff. Oats can be used as oat meal, oat flour, oat bran and oat flakes as breakfast cereals and as ingredients in other food stuffs. Oats are one of the most nutritious grain cereals, high in protein and fiber. Oat protein is generally greater than that found in other cereal grains. It contains high amount of vitamins and minerals (Giwa and Abiodun, 2010). Oats are grown for use as grain as well as forage and fodder, straw for bedding, hay, haylage, silage and chaff. Oat is an important winter fodder, mostly fed as green but surplus is converted into silage or hay to use during fodder deficit periods. Oat as a forage crop has the advantage of being winter hardy and serves as catch crop

SAMPLE PREPARATION

Method of production of Pancake

The pancake recipe set used are shown below. The egg was poured into a wide bowl with the sugar and mixed together using a wooden spatula, after which the minced onions, pepper, salt and milk(ingredients) was added together and mixed thoroughly, gradually the flour was added and mixed thoroughly as well. After which the water was also added when the pancake batter seems too thick, stirring continued until it became smooth. The pan was placed on heat with a little oil on it to grease the whole surface until hot. Using a spoon, the pancake batter was scooped and poured into the hot pan. One side of the pancake batter was fried for 3 min, flipped over to the other side and fried for another 3 min.

Fig. 3.3: Flow chart for pancake production

SAMPLE FORMULATIO

SAMPLE	OAT FLOUR%	AUBERGINE FLOUR%
IMS	95	5
ISM	90	10
MIS	85	15
MSI	80	20

IMS- Pancakes produced from 95% oat flour and 5% Aubergine flour

ISM- Pancakes produced from 90% oat flour and 10% Aubergine flour

MIS- Pancakes produced from 85% oat flour and 15% Aubergine flour

MSI- Pancakes produced from 80% oat flour and 20% Aubergine flour

METHODS

The proximate Analysis was determined using the standard methods as described by (AOAC, 2006). Functional analysis were carried by method stipulated by Quatitative analysis while the hedonic scale was used to evaluate the sensory characteristics

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 4.1 Proximate composition of keto-pancake produced from Aubergine and Oat flour blend

Properties/ samples(%)	IMS	ISM	MIS	MSI
Moisture content	55.69 ± 0.01	57.65 ± 0.07	58.37 ± 0.03	58.45 ± 0.04
Dry matter	45.32 ± 0.01	42.35 ± 0.01	41.63 ± 0.03	41.56 ± 0.04
Ash content	1.69 ± 0.01	1.65 ± 0.00	1.78 ± 0.00	1.86 ± 0.01
Protein	4.67 ± 0.01	4.34 ± 0.02	4.77 ± 0.01	5.30 ± 0.03
Fat	1.84 ± 0.06	2.63 ± 0.04	2.76 ± 0.03	3.25 ± 0.01
Fibre content	0.85 ± 0.02	0.93 ± 0.01	0.81 ± 0.01	0.92 ± 0.00
Carbohydrate	35.28 ± 0.08	32.81 ± 0.20	31.51 ± 0.09	30.23 ± 0.09

Values obtained are triplicate with mean ± standard deviation

Table 4.2 Functional properties of keto-pancake produced from aubergine and oat flour blend

Properties/ Samples	IMS	ISM	MIS	MSI
Bulk density (g/ml)	0.604 ± 0.01	0.595 ± 0.01	0.539 ± 0.01	0.567 ± 0.01
True density (g/ml)	0.295 ± 0.001	0.280 ± 0.001	0.288 ± 0.000	0.285 ± 0.001
Foaming capacity (%)	32.50 ± 4.00	22.50 ± 4.00	32.50 ± 4.00	22.50 ± 4.00
Emulsification cap (%)	62.25 ± 0.40	61.00 ± 1.00	50.25 ± 0.40	27.79 ± 0.30
Gelation cap (%w/v)	89.00 ± 1.00	87.00 ± 1.00	91.00 ± 1.00	94.50 ± 0.70
pH	6.61 ± 0.01	6.25 ± 0.03	6.09 ± 0.02	5.99 ± 0.02
Wettability (sec)	9.82 ± 0.30	7.90 ± 0.10	11.75 ± 0.40	9.65 ± 0.50
WAC (g/g)	10.44 ± 0.01	10.38 ± 0.02	11.97 ± 2.00	10.54 ± 0.20
OAC(g/g)	9.55 ± 0.01	9.67 ± 0.20	9.58 ± 0.02	9.36 ± 0.02

Values obtained are triplicate with mean ± standard deviation

Table 4.3 Sensory properties of keto-pancake produced from aubergine and oat flour blend

Properties/ samples(%)	IMS	ISM	MIS	MSI	LSD
Taste	5.10 ^a	4.90 ^a	4.60 ^a	4.10 ^a	4.40
Colour	5.10 ^c	4.80 ^c	4.10 ^c	3.70 ^c	4.04
Aroma	4.80 ^a	3.40 ^a	4.60 ^a	4.50 ^a	5.66
Texture	6.30 ^{ab}	5.00 ^b	5.00 ^b	4.70 ^b	5.25
General acceptability	5.60 ^a	4.40 ^a	4.30 ^a	4.20 ^a	4.44

Table 1 shows the proximate composition of keto-pancake samples, it was revealed that the moisture content ranged from 55.69% to 58.45% with sample MIS having the lowest moisture content (58.37%) while sample MSI having the highest value of 58.45%). This study was similar to that of Obasi *et al.*, (2012) who conducted and prepare pancake using composite flour used for production of pancake with the value about (45.44%. to 80.40%) . Moisture content is the ratio of the mass of water in a sample to the mass of solid in the sample. Dry matter ranged from 41.56% to 45.32% with sample MSI having the lowest value of (41.46%) while sample IMS having the highest value of (45.32%). Dry matter is the portion of a food product that remains after all water has been removed; it includes all non-water components like carbohydrates, fats, proteins, vitamins, minerals, and fiber. The ash content ranged from 1.69% to 1.86% with sample ISM having the lowest value of (1.69%) while sample MSI having the highest value of (1.865). The ash content can be defined as the inorganic residue that remains after combustion of the food sample in air at specific high temperature and it is carried out to determine the type and amount of mineral in food.

The protein content ranged from 4.67% to 5.30% with sample ISM had the lowest value of (4.67% to MSI had the highest value of (5.30%). The result of Olaoye *et al.*, (2006) is in agreement with this current result, in his observation on the production of pancakes produced from wheat flour and carrot powder with the value of 4.44% to 4.10%. Protein is the building blocks for the body repair and function (Okmen *et al.*, 2009). The fat content ranged from 1.84% to 3.25% with sample

IMS having the lowest value of fat content (1.84%) while sample MSI having the highest value of (3.25%). This result is in agreement with result reported by (Giami and Barber, 2004) who reported the fat content of the pancakes produced from composite flours of wheat and corn flour fortified with carrot powder with value of 1.80% to 3.15%. The fat content of the sample did not vary much as the same quantities of fat, fat in food brings about rancidity which is a term used to describe the oxygen damage in food and it result in change in odour, flavour and taste and the food is not recommended for consumption.

The fibre content of the sample ranged from 0.85% to 0.92% with sample MIS having the lowest value of 0.81% while sample LSM having the highest value of (0.93%). Other studies have shown that combining wheat and oat flour resulted and increased the dietary fiber alone. fiber content in food helps in easy digesting and bowel movement (constipation). The fiber content, this is the measure of the quantity of indigestible cellulose, pentosans, lignin and other components of the type in present food. The carbohydrate content ranged from 35.28% to 30.23% with sample MSI having the lowest value of (30.23%) while sample IMS having the highest value (35.28%). Carbohydrate gives energy to the body. It is the fuel of the brain and muscles.

Table 2 represents the result of the Functional properties of keto-pancake produced from aubergine and oat flour blend; Bulk density ranged from 0.604g/ml to 0.567g/ml, sample MIS having the lowest value of (0.539%) with sample IMS had the highest value of (0.604%). These results are in agreement with (Adebowale *et al.*, 2012) on the production of keto-pancakes produced with wheat flour, corn flour and carrot powder with the value of 0.426g/ml to 0.379g/ml. Bulk density of a food material is important in relation to its packaging. Solomon *et al.*, (2017) reported that increase in bulk density is desirable in that, it offers greater packaging and advantage as greater quantity may be parked with constant volume. True density ranged from 0.29g/ml to 0.285g/ml, sample LSM having the lowest value of (0.295g/ml) while sample IMS having the highest value of (0.295g/ml). Omal and Djamel (2018)

records on the pancakes from wheat, fonio flour fortified with banana flavour with value of 0.30g/ml to 0.25g/ml is in agreement with the current study. In food products, true density is the mass of a sample divided by its true volume, excluding all open and closed pores within the material. The foam capacity of the samples ranged from 232.50% to 22.50% with sample IMS and MSI had the lowest value of (22.50%). There was a gradual increase in foam capacity with increasing addition of raw maize. Satam *et al.* (2013) also reported the decreasing effect of processing conditions on foam capacity with processed oat grain. The more pronounced reduction in foam capacity in heat-treated sample has been attributed to protein denaturation. It is also an indication of precipitation of proteins due to temperature and some heat treatment. This is a similar report observed by Okpala *et al.*, (2013) on determination of foaming capacity of composite flour for production of Pancake. Foaming capacity are parameters in the characterization of functional properties of protein. The foaming properties depend on their ability to form flexible, elastic, cohesive interfacial film.

Emulsification capacity measures the ability of sufficiently soluble proteins to migrate to the water or oil interface and environmental conditions, like pH and ionic strength, influence the emulsifying capacity of proteins by affecting their solubility. The Emulsification capacity ranged 62.25% to 27.79% with sample MSI (having the lowest value of (27.79%) while sample IMS having the highest value of (62.25%). According to Saeedifar *et al.*, (2014) similar report of emulsion capacity shows in some pancake produced from oat and cashew flour by the researcher with the value of 61.20% to 205.70 %. Capacity measures the ability of sufficiently soluble protein in the samples.

Gelation capacity refers to the ability of food ingredients like proteins, starches, or fiber to form a firm, three-dimensional gel network that traps water and other components. Gelation is influenced by factors like protein/starch structure, heat, pH, water content, and the presence of other ingredients (Djouadi *et al.*, 2016) Gelation capacity ranged from 18.39%w/v to 18.778%w/v with sample MIS having the lowest value of (17.87%w/v) with sample MSI having the highest value of

(18.78%w/v). This process is crucial for texture, stability, and moisture retention in many foods, such as dairy products, processed meats, and baked goods. This process is crucial for texture, stability, and moisture retention in many foods, such as dairy products, processed meats, and baked goods (Dias, 2012). The gelatinization temperature of the formulated samples varied from 89.00°C to 94.50°C. Sample IMS having the lowest value of (89.00°C) while sample MSI having the highest value of (94.50°C). The gradual reduction in the gelation with increasing malted sorghum ratio may be as a result of high fiber content which is known to have a high water absorption capacity and thus does not thicken or gel on heating (Wasserman, 2010).

The pH content of the samples ranged from 6.61 to 5.99 with sample MSI having the lowest pH value of (5.00) while sample IMS having the highest value of (6.61). pH is the measure of how acidic or basic a substance is. In humans, pH balance plays a role in keeping the body functioning optimally. While a universal pH value for all keto pancakes cannot be given, typical research on wheat and other flours suggests pH values for pancakes range from approximately 4.0 to 7.3, depending on the flour type, the use of acid-activated leavening (like baking soda), and other ingredient variations. The results obtained for water absorption capacity of the samples ranged from 10.44g/g to 10.54g/g with sample ISM having the lowest value of (10.38g/g) with sample MIS having the highest value of (11.97g/g). This result is similar to that of (Mibei et al., 2007) on the production of pancakes from wheat flour and groundnut powder with the value of 2.60g/g to 2.10g/g. Thus, swelling on exposure to moisture. Similar values were obtained from keto pancakes from oat flour and carrot powder (Mibei et al., 2007). Water absorption refers to the ability of material to absorb water when immersed in it and is represented with water absorbing capacity. The oil absorption capacity (OAC) of the samples varied in trend from those obtained for water absorption capacity. The values ranged from 9.55g/g to 9.36g/g with sample MSI having the lowest value of (9.36g/g) while sample ISM having the highest value of (9.67g/g). The hydrophobicity of proteins is known to play a major role in fat absorption. This acts to resist physical entrapment of oil by the

capillary of non-polar side chains of the amino acids of the protein molecules (Adebowale et al., 2012).

From the table 3, Taste is closely related to smell. The perception of odor and taste, combined with trigeminal sensations, results in the overall flavor. Flavor influences food acceptance and selection of food intake, and helps us to distinguish potentially harmful compounds. The result ranged from 5.10^a to 4.10^a with sample MSI had the lowest taste value of (4.10^a) while sample IMS had the highest value of (5.10^a) Sample IMS is highly preferred by the panelist for its taste, there is a significant different among all the samples ($p < 0.05$). Color is a food quality sensory attribute that is essential to a consumer's judgment and food acceptability such as flavor, and texture, which can be used as a predictor for non-quality attributes like MC, over-processing, and pigment content (Clydesdale, 2011). The colour ranged from 75.10^c to 3.70^c with sample MSI had the lowest value of (3.70^c) while sample IMS had the highest value of (5.10^c), sample MSI is least preferred with value of (3.70^b). There was no significant different among the five samples ($p < 0.05$). Food colour gives consumers an almost immediate impression about the freshness, flavour and quality of a product.

Aroma are chemical senses stimulated by the chemical properties of odor molecules which must reach the olfactory bulb to interact with olfactory cells in the olfactory mucosa. Smells are detected by breathing air that carries odor molecules. The aroma ranged from 4.80^a to 4.50^a . Sample ISM had the lowest value of (4.10^a) while sample IMS had the highest value of (4.80^a) There is a significant different ($p > 0.05$) among the sample. The aroma (smell, odor, fragrance) of food is one of the most important sensory impressions and in most cases determines the choice and acceptance of the product by the consumer. Texture analysis plays a very important role in sensory evaluation and development of a new food product. Food texture is a collective term of sensory experiences originated from visual, audio and tactile stimuli. The texture of the samples ranged from 6.30^b to 4.70^b with sample MSI had the lowest value of (4.70^b) while sample IMS had the highest value of (6.30^b). There is no significant difference among the

sample ($p < 0.05$). The overall acceptability of the samples ranged from 5.60^a to 4.20^a , with sample MSI had the lowest value of (4.20^a) while sample IMS had the highest value of (5.60^a). Sample IMS have the highest overall acceptability than other samples.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study showed that production of keto-pancake from oat flour and aubergine flour can be produced but the inclusion of aubergine flour changes the colour of the keto-pancake but it can be edible but less in colour preferable. From the proximate analysis, various constituents like moisture, protein, fat, ash, carbohydrate, crude fiber and energy among four samples. The study successfully demonstrated the potential of using oat flour and aubergine flour as alternative low-carbohydrate ingredients in the production of keto-friendly pancakes.

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